

A Psychoanalytic Exploration of Trauma in Celeste Ng's "Little Fires Everywhere"

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Abstract

This study provides a psychoanalytic exploration of trauma in Celeste Ng's *Little Fires Everywhere*, employing psychoanalytic theory to interpret the characters' psychological experiences and the broader thematic implications of the novel. Utilizing foundational concepts from Freud's theories of repression and defense mechanisms (Freud, 1920), as well as Klein's object relations theory (Klein, 1932) and Lacan's notion of the mirror stage (Lacan, 1977), the research delves into how trauma is portrayed through the characters' behaviors and interactions. The analysis reveals that the characters' psychological distress is deeply intertwined with familial relationships and societal expectations. The study finds that Elena Richardson's controlling behavior and adherence to societal norms are manifestations of her repressed anxieties and unresolved guilt. Her perfectionism and critical stance towards others reflect deeper psychological conflicts rooted in past traumas. Conversely, Mia Warren's art is interpreted as a form of sublimation, redirecting repressed grief into creative expression, which aligns with Freud's (1920) theory. Mia's reluctance to forge close relationships and her secretive nature are seen as mechanisms for managing her trauma, illustrating the influence of early relational dynamics on psychological coping strategies. Furthermore, the research highlights how the socio-economic divide between the Richardson and Warren families exacerbates psychological distress, underscoring the interplay between personal trauma and broader social structures. The findings emphasize that trauma in *Little Fires Everywhere* is not merely an individual experience but is also shaped by familial and societal contexts. By integrating psychoanalytic concepts with literary analysis, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of trauma representation in contemporary literature and offers insights relevant for both literary scholarship and psychoanalytic practice.

Keywords: Celeste Ng, Defense Mechanisms, *Little Fires Everywhere*, Mirror Stage, Psychoanalytic Theory, Psychological Distress, Repression Trauma

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